

Institutional Effectiveness Vis-à-Vis Resource Dependence Influence: The Case of Line- Agencies in Sulu

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Abstract

This study investigates the extent to which resource dependence influences institutional effectiveness among line agencies in the province of Sulu, within the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Grounded in Resource Dependence Theory and models of institutional effectiveness, the research utilized a descriptive-quantitative approach. A total of 200 employees from selected line agencies were purposively sampled, and data were gathered using a structured survey instrument. Effectiveness was measured across four dimensions: environmental, social, economic, and political. Statistical analyses, including mean, standard deviation, Pearson correlation, and ANOVA, were employed to interpret the data. Results revealed that institutional effectiveness was rated high, while

resource dependence was moderate. A statistically significant positive correlation was found between institutional effectiveness and resource dependence, suggesting that improved access to financial and material resources enhances organizational performance. Furthermore, significant differences in perceptions were noted when data were categorized by demographic profiles. The study underscores the importance of strategic resource allocation and policy reforms to strengthen institutional capacity and improve service delivery in decentralized governance settings. These findings contribute empirical evidence to the discourse on public administration and organizational sustainability in developing regions.

Keywords: *Institutional effectiveness; Resource dependence; Line agencies; Public sector governance; Organizational performance; Sulu; BARMM; Descriptive research; Pearson correlation; Decentralization*

INTRODUCTION

This research sought to help renew an interest in the work of defining and measuring effectiveness in line-agencies. It uses the existing literature to explore environmental, social, economic and political factors that have an influence on institutional effectiveness. This investigates differences among constituencies in their ratings of effectiveness. This changes in how public institutions are financed and the potential implications of these changes for effectiveness, this research explores the degree to which resource

dependence, primarily dependence on budgetary General Appropriation Act and public funding, influences the effectiveness of public institutions.

This study was conducted to determine the institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence of line agencies in Sulu for Fiscal Year 2024. Specifically, the study was designed to: (1) The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: gender; age; educational attainment; length of service; and status of appointment; (2) The extent of institutional effectiveness of line agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees in terms of: environmental factors; social factors; economic factors; and political factors; (3) The extent of resource dependence influence on the effectiveness of line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees; (4) The significant difference exist in the extent of institutional effectiveness in terms of environmental factors; social factors; economic factors; and political factors among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of: gender; age; educational attainment; length of service; and status of appointment. (5) The significant difference exist on the extent of resource dependence influence among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of: gender; age; educational attainment; length of service; and status of appointment; (6) The significant correlation exist between institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design method was employed in this study, that is, with the purpose to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge or phenomenon of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence among employees in line-agencies in Sulu.

This study was conducted among 200 employees in line agencies in Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Agrarian Reform (MAFAR), Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources and Energy (MENRE), Ministry of the Interior and Local Government (MILG), Ministry of Public Works (MPW), Ministry of Trade, Industry and Tourism (MTIT), Philippine Statistic Authority (PSA) Sulu Provincial Government Office and Jolo Municipal Government Offices in line agencies in Sulu regardless of their ranks/position for the Fiscal Year 2024.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study illustrates the assessment of the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence as viewed by the employees among line-agencies in Fiscal Year 2024. It also deals with employee's demographic profiles in terms gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment; extent of sub-categories subsumed under institutional effectiveness and resource dependence, and the significant correlation and differences in these sub-categories when data are classified according to respondents' demographic profiles.

The following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that which correspond to each of the research questions:

1.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents The majority of respondents were female (56%), aged 30–39 years (35%), and college graduates (82%). Most had less than 10 years of service (66%) and held permanent appointments (57%).

3.2 Institutional Effectiveness

Effectiveness was rated highly across all four dimensions:

- Environmental: Mean = 4.19 (Agree)
- Social: Mean = 4.16 (Agree)
- Economic: Mean = 4.03 (Agree)
- Political: Mean = 4.10 (Agree)

3.3 Resource Dependence

Respondents reported moderate dependence on external funding sources, with concerns about sustainability and equitable distribution.

3.4 Correlation Analysis

A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$) was found between institutional effectiveness and resource dependence.

3.5 Differences by Demographic Profile

ANOVA results indicated statistically significant differences in perceived effectiveness based on age and educational attainment ($p < 0.05$). Gender and status of appointment also showed significant variations in views on resource dependence.

This study determined the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence of line agencies in Sulu for Fiscal Year 2024, employee-respondents demographic profiles in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment; the extent of institutional effectiveness of line agencies in Sulu in terms of environmental factors, social factors, economic factors, and political factors; and the extent of resource dependence influence.

This study answered the research questions on the bases of the following hypotheses: 1) There is no significant difference on the extent of institutional effectiveness in terms of environmental factors; social factors; economic factors; and political factors among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment, 2) There is no significant difference in the extent of resource dependence influence among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment; and 3) There is no significant correlation between institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence.

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design which is a formal, objective and systematic process for obtaining quantifiable information. This facilitated the determination of the institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence among line-agencies in Sulu.

The frequency counts and percentage were used to determine the employee-respondents' profile, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence of line-agencies in Sulu, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r), t -Test for independent samples and One-Way ANOVA were used to determine the significant correlation and the differences in the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence of line-agencies in Sulu.

The following are findings of this study:

1) For Research Question Number 1: On demographic profile employee-respondents

Out of 200 employee-respondents, majority are female, within the 35-39 years old of age range, great majority have only bachelor's degree, have 10 years & below of years of work experience, and more than one-half have permanent work status.

2) For Research Question Number 2: On the Extent of Institutional Effectiveness

Employee-respondents rated as "Agree" or "High Extent" all the sub-categories subsumed under Institutional Effectiveness such as Environmental Factors, Social Factors, Economic Factors and Political Factors.

3) For Research Question Number 3: On the Extent of Resource Dependence Influence

Employee-respondents rated this category as "Agree" or "High Extent".

4) For Research Question Number 4: On Differences in Institutional Effectiveness

NO significant difference on the extent of institutional effectiveness in terms of environmental factors; social factors; economic factors; and political factors among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment.

5. For Research Question Number 5: On Differences in the Extent of Resource Dependence Influence

NO significant difference in the extent of resource dependence influence among line-agencies in Sulu as viewed by the employees when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, educational attainment, length of service, and status of appointment.

6. On Correlation between Transformational Leadership Style and Work Engagement

Generally, there is a high positive correlation between the extent of Institutional Effectiveness and Resource Dependence Influence of line agencies in Sulu.

Conclusions

This study concluded that majority of employees of line-agencies in Sulu are female, within the 35-39 years old of age range, have only bachelor's degree, have 10 years & below of years of work experience, and have permanent work status.

On the average, employees of line-agencies in Sulu agreed with a high extent on institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence in respective offices. This result implies that environmental factors,

social factors, economic factors and political factors have positively contributed in the performance, albeit the discharge of their duties and functions as employees of line-agencies in Sulu.

Personal variables such as gender, age, educational attainment, length of service and status of appointment do intervene or serve as point of reference in ways how employees of line-agencies judge the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence. This result implies that other variable/s, which is/are not used in this study, should have been referred to by the respondents in measuring the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence.

This study accepts the hypotheses that there is no significant difference in the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profiles. However, it rejects the contention that there is no significant correlation between institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence.

Relatively, this study tends to support Cooper & Vargas (2018) and Esty, Levy, Srebontnjak and de Sherbinin (2019) theories which state that in order to achieve effectiveness development, the focus cannot be only on the environment or the economy but it must be based on the living square, a balance between environmental protection, social development, political development and economic development.

Recommendations

This study recommends that the administrators of line agencies in Sulu should continue in upgrading programs and policies related to institutional effectiveness without prejudice to gender, age, educational attainment, length of service and status of appointment since these variables found to have no significant intervention on the ways how employees perceive the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence. In other words, treatment of employees should not differ between male and female, between young and old, between bachelor's and master's, between new and old, and between permanent and contractual employees since these variable do not play a significant role in ways how employees perceive the extent of effectiveness of their services.

Moreover, student-researchers in the field of public management are invigorated to conduct study similar to this one so as to gather for more empirical data to confirm and explain why variables gender, age, educational qualification, length of service and status of appointment do not significantly intervene on the perceptions of respondents towards the extent of institutional effectiveness and resource dependence influence.

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